

Critical analysis of the primary circuit components important to LTO's safe operation of NPP VVER 440 and VVER 1000

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Abstract. The paper is focused on the identification of critical issues with the primary circuit components based on the operational experience with the importance of safe long-term operation (LTO) of VVER 440 and VVER1000 nuclear reactors. Results from the actual running H2020-Europe project DELISA-LTO are presented in cumulative form in detail. Our approach is to combine the development of the simulation tools, experimental work (material analyses), specific irradiations and in-service and/or non-destructive inspection techniques to develop the effective “early warning” tool for the assessment of the system integrity for the LTO of the current VVER reactors.

INTRODUCTION

Long and safe operation of nuclear power plants (NPP) is the basic requirement in nuclear power engineering. By the end of 2022, in total 427 power reactors were in operation and 56 new reactors are under construction worldwide. The age distribution is presented in [1]. From this amount, 65 VVER reactors are in operation in 12 countries and about 20 VVERs are under construction. In EU countries, 19 VVER units are in operation. The next 15 are in Ukraine. The high level of safe, effective, reliable, and long-term operation behind the projected lifetime of up to 60-80 years and without of former general designer is the real and actual challenge for the European nuclear community.

DEGRADATION MECHANISMS FOR SELECTED COMPONENTS OF VVERS

All NPP components degrade in time via **ageing**. More precisely, their mechanical properties degrade due to cyclic or static load. The most serious ageing processes are strain ageing and thermal ageing [2].

There are two types of strain ageing that can be distinguished: static strain ageing (SSA) and dynamic strain ageing (DSA). Static strain ageing refers to the hardening of a material that has undergone plastic deformation and which is subsequently aged for a period. The strengthening effect results from the diffusion of solute atoms to dislocations during ageing. The formation of solute atmospheres around dislocations effectively pins, at least temporarily, the dislocations and restrains them from further movement upon reloading; these events consequently lead to an increase in the yield strength. A higher stress is then required to tear the dislocations away from the solute atmospheres. Strain ageing may also increase the ultimate tensile strength, reduce the ductility, and raise the ductile-to-brittle transition temperature. Generally, in steel, the elements responsible for strain ageing are carbon and nitrogen. This is due to the significantly higher diffusivities of interstitial solutes compared to substitutional solutes. The diffusivities are also a strong function of temperature and thus, the extent of strengthening depends on the ageing temperature as well as the ageing time [3].

In the case of dynamic strain ageing, the ageing process occurs during deformation. Solute atoms possess enough mobility to catch up with the moving dislocations and impede dislocation motion during deformation. Dislocations become temporarily pinned by obstacles, at which time solute atoms diffuse to the dislocations and lock them. DSA develops when the diffusivity of the solute atoms approaches the dislocation velocity. The occurrence of DSA is

therefore dependent on temperature and strain rate: the diffusivity is a function of temperature while the dislocation velocity is governed by the strain rate [3].

Thermal ageing is a temperature, material state (microstructure) and time-dependent degradation mechanism. The material may lose ductility and become brittle because of very small microstructural changes in the form of precipitates coming out of a solid solution. In the case of RPV steel with impurity copper, the important precipitates are copper-rich (however, there could be other precipitates). The precipitates block dislocation movement thereby causing hardening and embrittlement [4]. Thermal ageing is a phenomenon occurring in steels with a content of carbon less than 0.2% and is related to the amount of nitrogen dissolved in steel.

An important degradation process in the primary circuit (especially close to the reactor core where thermal or neutron loads are higher) is **embrittlement**. According to factors causing embrittlement, we could distinguish [5]:

- Thermal embrittlement.
- Hydrogen embrittlement.
- Radiation embrittlement.

Thermal embrittlement is a phenomenon occurring in CrMo steels and leading to a decrease in their elasticity. This degradation mechanism is caused by segregation processes of elements like Sb, Sn, As and P on prior austenite grain boundaries at 350-600°C and leads to a decrease in the cohesive strength of boundaries. Elements such as C, Mn, Ni, Si, Cr and Mo accelerate the embrittlement of these steels. By monitoring chemical composition and maintaining parameters of heat treatment during the manufacture of RPV, these phenomena do not present a significant problem.

In general, hydrogen negatively affects and could cause a significant change in the physical properties of materials. Several factors have a significant influence on hydrogen embrittlement such as material strength, amount of diffused hydrogen and stress state. Because of its small size, hydrogen is capable of diffusing into the material very fast even at ambient temperature. Penetration of atomic hydrogen into the steels could cause an enormous decrease in material ductility. Materials could be susceptible to cracks and formation of the brittle fractures during the loading under the yield strength – occurrence of delayed fractures. During the diffusion, atomic hydrogen uses crystal lattice defects such as grain boundaries to penetrate the steel.

In RPV, hydrogen embrittlement is caused by absorption of H₂. This hydrogen arises in the primary circuit of NPP due to i) radiolysis of the coolant ii) corrosive effects of the coolant and iii) high-temperature dissociation of water.

The embrittlement of RPV is due to the absorption of atomic hydrogen. Austenitic cladding of the inner surface of VVER-440 RPV prevents absorption of hydrogen, however, if the cladding is disrupted this process could locally occur.

The source of the radiation (β , γ , n, ν) in NPP is the nuclear fission reaction in fuel, which is in the active zone inside RPV. Two types of energy are released during the fission chain reaction: kinetic energy of fission fragments and energy released during the decay of fission fragments. The kinetic energy of all types of particles transforms into thermal energy during their crossing through ambient matter. RPV is exposed to radiation consisting of a mixture of gamma photons, beta particles, fission products and neutrons of various energies [6].

During the irradiation of metallic materials with particles such as neutrons, protons and electrons with sufficiently high energy, these incident particles interact with the material leading to dynamic disturbances and changes in the microstructure of the material (shifting of atoms from their regular positions in crystal lattice). These processes lead to the formation of crystal lattice defects affecting the macroscopic properties of the material. As these incident particles cross through the crystal lattice, they interact with the lattice atoms transferring energy to them. These interactions could damage the crystal lattice and can be divided into three types [5]:

- The production of shifted atoms from their regular lattice positions (displacement damage).
- Changes in chemical composition when the incident particle is stopped in material (ion implantation) or captured by atomic nuclei (transmutation).
- The excitation of electrons and the ionization of atoms (not permanent damage).

The elementary interaction occurring between the crystal lattice atoms and the incident particles is collision. This interaction occurs in a time of $<10^{-17}$ s. These collisions lead to changes in the direction of motion of the incident particles, known as scattering. Collisions could be either elastic or inelastic. An elastic collision is an encounter between two particles in which the total kinetic energy of the two particles after the encounter is equal to their total kinetic energy before the encounter. Elastic collisions occur only if there is no net conversion of kinetic energy into other forms. An inelastic collision, in contrast to an elastic collision, is a collision in which kinetic energy is not conserved due to the action of internal friction and some of the original energy is lost [5].

Irradiation embrittlement involves many variables. The most important are: i) irradiation temperature, ii) neutron fluence and neutron flux, and iii) chemical composition of irradiated steels.

About 70-80% of the embrittlement effect is attributed to the metallic clusters or the coherent Cu clusters or precipitates. The influence of the Cu clusters and P clusters is attributed to an age or precipitation hardening mechanism. The importance of Ni content in the embrittlement process has become apparent, but the physical role of Ni is not well understood [7].

Fatigue is defined as the structural deterioration that occurs as a result of repeated stress/strain cycles caused by fluctuating loads and temperatures. After repeated cyclic loading of sufficient magnitude, microstructural damage can accumulate, leading to macroscopic crack initiation at the most highly affected locations. Subsequent continued cyclic loading can lead to the growth of the initiated crack. Fatigue behaviour is related to a variety of parameters, such as stress range, mean stress, cycling frequency, surface roughness and environmental conditions. Cracks initiate at stress concentrations such as geometric notches and surface defects. Fatigue crack initiation curves indicate how many stress cycles it takes to initiate fatigue cracks in components. These curves are materials-related and indicate the allowable number of stress cycles for applied cyclic stress amplitudes.

The environment can significantly influence fatigue crack initiation. Environmentally assisted fatigue, often referred to as corrosion fatigue must be considered when dealing with components in the Pressurized Water Reactor (PWR) environment. There are three sources of fatigue significant to the PWR. These are system cycling, thermal cycling and flow-induced vibration.

System cycling refers to changes in the reactor system, which cause variations in pressure and temperature. Examples of system cycling are startup, shutdown, SCRAM, and safety/relief valve blowdown. System cycling was the best-understood source of fatigue during the time of vessel design.

Fatigue thermal cycling may occur due to temperature fluctuations. Temperature transients during operation can cause local or global temperature gradients, resulting in thermal cycling at the interface of material and environment. Smooth and sharp temperature transients result in slow or rapid thermal cycling, both being a source for accumulation of fatigue usage. Causes for smooth transients are generally start-up and shutdown procedures or load following operation modes.

Flow-induced vibration is caused when coolant flowing past a component sheds vortices which create cyclic loads. These loads generally occur in a frequency range up to about 20 Hz, leading to the expectation that flow-induced vibration cycles accumulate early in operation, probably during pre-operation tests. However, some modes of flow-induced vibration may be associated with a particular operating mode, which occurs infrequently [8].

Corrosion is the reaction of a substance with its environment that causes a detectable change which can lead to deterioration in the function of the component or structure. In the present context, the material is steel, and the reaction is usually an electrochemical reaction. The appearance of corrosion is governed by the so-called corrosion system consisting of the metal and the corrosive medium (the environment) with all the participating elements that can influence the electrochemical behaviour and the corrosion parameters. The variety of possible chemical and physical variables leads to many types of corrosion [4]:

- Corrosion without mechanical loading (general corrosion and local corrosion attack, selective corrosion attack as e.g. intergranular corrosion).
- Corrosion with mechanical loading (stress corrosion cracking, corrosion fatigue) and synergistic effects of neutron irradiation (irradiation-assisted stress corrosion cracking).
- Flow-induced corrosion attack (e.g., erosion corrosion).

During the electrochemical processes, the metal ions dissolve in the liquid electrolyte (anodic dissolution) and hydrogen is produced. This is the process of material loss and the creation of corrosion products. When mechanical stresses or strains are also present, the anodic dissolution of the metal can be stimulated, protection layers (oxide layers) can rupture or hydrogen interaction with the metal (absorption) can be promoted which can produce secondary damage. The combined action of a corrosive environment and mechanical loading can cause cracking even when no material degradation occurs under either the chemical or the mechanical conditions alone.

Water chemistry control during operation, as well as during shutdown, is very important for avoiding corrosion problems. Thus, the content of all additives has to be carefully monitored and the ingress of impurities has to be strictly avoided, e.g. during standstill periods and maintenance work.

Finally, it is necessary to consider also **swelling**. This process depends on neutron fluence and temperature. Radiation swelling is an increase in the size and change in the shape of metal due to forming pores and clusters of interstitial atoms in its structure, which arise and grow under the influence of high doses of neutron irradiation. Radiation swelling can lead to unacceptable changes in the geometry of reactor internal (RI) components, which causes a violation of the coolant flow conditions, mutual deformation oppression of RI parts and occurrence of compensation stresses, as well as additional metal embrittlement, which can limit the service life of RI components.

Besides that, modern models of swelling include dependencies from stresses and consider the process of creep. The value of swelling increases during NPP operation and requires additional assessments of thermal-hydraulic

parameters and strength of pressure vessel internals. The process of swelling is one of the limiting factors of LTO of VVER-1000 which has a direct relation to safety margins. On the other hand, mechanism swelling almost does not occur in the reactors of the VVER 440 type. Swelling can occur very limited only by baffle bolts in specific areas of core baffle, the development of swelling is minimal according to actual information.

CONCLUSION

It is generally accepted that for VVER-440 units the most critical part is the reactor pressure vessel which practically cannot be changed. Due to the specific design considering transport difficulties by track or train, the core-vessel distance was minimized. The VVER RPV wall fluence is about five times higher compared with the western PWRs [2,9].

Besides the RPV, another critical part of the VVER-440 units is the six steam generators. The leaking steam generator pipes cannot be repaired, only plugging is available. After a certain number of plugging the steam generator (SG) capacity is going below the criteria. Particularly, i) SG primary tubes with 16 mm diameter (dominantly welds at collectors where special technology based on explosion was used and presented Cl accelerated corrosion processes) and ii) SG feat water pipelines (where corrosion of secondary pipelines (carbon steel GOST 22K) was so heavy that some parts could damage primary tubes in SG) were recognized as permanent appearing problem which had to be solved during last 40 years. In the case of VVER-1000, the reactor pressure vessel is relatively widely distanced from the core and neutron embrittlement causes not so significant degradation as in the case of VVER-440. The operation experience of VVER-1000 confirms that the following are considered the most critical components: i) Welded joint of primary circuit SG collector and SG nozzle Ø1200, ii) Pressurizer surge line and iii) SG heat exchanger tubes (HET).

As other critical issues occurred (at both VVER-440 as well as VVER-1000 types) could be mentioned welds in general, mostly dissimilar welds, pressurizers, and heat exchangers. Proper maintenance, in-service inspections as well as adequate training and knowledge of operating staff could minimize the scope of degradation, damages, and improve the NPP lifetime extension.

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